

Protocol of search strategy: The nexus of health and labour exploitation among migrant populations in the Eastern Mediterranean region and Türkiye: a scoping review

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Overview of the keywords

Keyword	Variations
Migrant	Migration, Immigrant, Transient, Emigrant, Foreign, Third Country National, Non-citizen, Non-native, Migratory status
Legal/residence migration status	Resident, Residence, Undocumented, Illegal, Irregular, Refugee, Asylum Seeker, Unaccompanied Minor, Unaccompanied Migrant, Unaccompanied Child
Decent work	Work, Labour, Employment, Job, Occupation, Domestic Work, Textile Industry, Fishing, Farming, Agriculture, Forestry, Plantation, Sex Work, Construction Industry, Mining, Manual Low-Skilled Jobs, Low Skilled, Informal Labor, Gig Work, Daily Wage Labor, Logging Industry, Timber Industry
Labour exploitation	Exploitative Practice, Exploitation, Exploitative Labour, Cheap Labour, Modern Slavery, Workplace Hazard, Hazardous Work, Dehumanisation, Coercion, Occupational Accident, Working Condition, Occupational Exposure, Workplace Violence, Precarious Employment, Seasonal Worker, Low Wages, Underpayment, Adverse Working Condition, Poor Working Condition, Adverse Work Experiences, Abuse At Work, Harassment At Work, Work-Related Illness
Modern slavery and Human trafficking	Human Trafficking, Trafficking In Human Beings, Sex Trafficking, Labour Trafficking, Child Trafficking, Trafficking, Forced Labour, Coerced Labour, Child Labour, Indentured Servitude, Debt Bondage, Domestic Servitude
Health	Occupational Health, Health, Health Services Accessibility, Access Health, Access To Primary Care, Healthcare Access, Healthcare Visit, Health Facility, Health Centre, Primary Care, Secondary Care, Tertiary Care, Mental Health Service, Psychosocial, Psychological Support,

	Psychosocial Support, Mental Health Support, Psychiatric Care, Social Support, Social Work, Hazard, Injury, Risk, Wellbeing, Well-Being, Sick, Ill, Occupational Health
Countries	Afghanistan, Bahrain, Djibouti, Egypt, Iran, Iraq, Jordan, Kuwait, Lebanon, Libya, Morocco, Oman, Pakistan, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, Somalia, Sudan, Syria, Tunisia, United Arab Emirates, Yemen, Türkiye, Eastern Mediterranean region, Middle East, Greater Middle East, Middle East and North Africa, MENA, Northern Africa, Arab world

Development of the general search string

Migra* OR Immigra* OR Transient OR Migrant OR Refugee OR Emigrant OR Immigrant OR "Undocumented Immigrant" OR "Undocumented Migrant" OR "Illegal Migrant" OR "Non Citizen" OR "Non-Citizen" OR "Non Native" OR "Non-Native" OR Foreign OR Resident OR "Asylum Seek*" OR Asylum OR "Unaccompanied Minor" OR "Unaccompanied Migrant" OR Undocumented OR Illegal OR Irregular OR "Third Country National*" OR "Unaccompanied Migrant Child*" OR "Labo?r Migra*" OR "Immigrant Work*" OR "Economic Migra*" OR "Economic Immigra*" OR "Migratory Status"
AND
"Labo?r Exploit*" OR "Exploitative Practic*" OR Exploitation OR "Exploitative Labo?r" OR "Human Traffick*" OR "Trafficking In Human Beings" OR "Sex Traffick*" OR "Labo?r Traffick*" OR "Child Traffick*" OR Traffick* OR "Forced Labo?r" OR "Coerced Labo?r" OR "Child Labo?r" OR "Indentured Servitude" OR "Debt Bondage" OR "Domestic Servitude" OR "Domestic Work" OR "Modern Slavery" OR "Manual Low-Skilled Job*" OR "Low Skilled" OR "Low-Skilled" OR "Workplace Hazard*" OR "Hazardous Work" OR Dehumanization OR Coercion OR "Occupational Accident*" OR "Working Condition*" OR "Occupational Exposure" OR "Workplace Violence" OR "Precarious Employment" OR "Seasonal Work*" OR "Low Wage*" OR Underpayment OR Labo?r OR "Adverse Working Condition*" OR "Poor Working Condition*" OR "Adverse Work Experience*" OR Farm* OR Agricultur* OR Fish* OR "Cheap Labo?r" OR Occupation* OR Work OR Employ* OR Mining OR Construction OR "Sex Work" OR Textile OR Plantation OR Forestr* OR "Informal Labo?r" OR "Gig Work" OR "Daily Wage Labo?r" OR "Logging Industry" OR "Timber Industry" OR "Abuse At Work" OR "Harassment At Work" OR "Work-Related Illness*"

AND

Health OR "Health Services Accessibility" OR "Access* Health*" OR "Access* To Primary Care" OR "Healthcare Access*" OR "Healthcare Visit*" OR "Health Facilit*" OR "Health Cent*" OR "Primary Care" OR "Secondary Care" OR "Tertiary Care" OR "Mental Health Service*" OR Psychosocial OR "Psychological Support" OR "Psychosocial Support" OR "Mental Health Support" OR "Psychiatric Care" OR "Social Support" OR "Social Work" OR Hazard* OR Injur* OR Risk* OR Wellbeing OR Well-Being OR Sick* OR Ill* OR "Occupational Health"

AND

Afghanistan OR Bahrain OR Djibouti OR Egypt OR Iran OR Iraq OR Jordan OR Kuwait OR Lebanon OR Libya OR Morocco OR Oman OR Pakistan OR Qatar OR "Saudi Arabia" OR Somalia OR Sudan OR Syria OR Tunisia OR "United Arab Emirates" OR UAE OR Yemen OR Türkiye OR Turkey OR "Eastern Mediterranean region" OR "Middle East" OR "Greater Middle East" OR "Middle East and North Africa" OR MENA OR "Northern Africa" OR "North Africa" OR "Arab world" OR "Arab Region"

Search strategies (procedure and syntax)

Timeframe: March 2011 until present.

PubMed

String number	Keyword	Syntax (All fields)
#1	Migrant and related euphemisms and proxies	("Transients and Migrants"[Mesh] OR "Refugees"[Mesh] OR "Emigrants and Immigrants"[Mesh] OR "Undocumented Immigrants"[Mesh] OR "Refugee Camps"[Mesh] OR "Emigration and Immigration"[Mesh] OR "Non-citizen" OR "Non citizen" OR "Non Native" OR "Non-native" OR "Foreign" OR "Resident" OR "Asylum Seeker" OR "Migrant" OR "Immigrant" OR "Unaccompanied Minor" OR "Unaccompanied Migrant" OR "Undocumented" OR "Illegal" OR "Irregular" OR "Third Country Nationals" OR "Labor Migra*" OR "Labour Migra*" OR "Immigrant Work*" OR "Economic Migra*" OR "Economic Immigra*" OR "Migratory Status")
#2	Labour exploitation	("Labor Exploit*" OR "Labour Exploit*" OR "Exploitative Practic*" OR "Exploitation" OR "Exploitative Labor" OR "Exploitative Labour" OR "Human Traffick*" OR "Trafficking In Human Beings" OR "Sex Trafficking" OR "Labor Traffick*" OR "Labour Traffick*" OR "Child Trafficking" OR "Trafficked" OR "Forced Labor" OR "Forced Labour" OR "Coerced Labor" OR "Coerced Labour" OR "Child Labor" OR "Child Labour" OR "Indentured Servitude" OR "Debt Bondage" OR "Domestic Servitude" OR "Domestic Work" OR "Modern Slavery" OR "Manual Low-Skilled Jobs" OR "Low Skilled" OR "Low-Skilled" OR "Workplace Hazard" OR "Hazardous Work" OR "Dehumanization" OR "Coercion" OR "Accidents, Occupational"[Mesh] OR "Working Condition" OR "Occupational Exposure" OR "Workplace Violence" OR "Precarious Employment" OR "Seasonal Worker" OR "Low Wages" OR "Underpayment" OR "Labor" OR "Labour" OR "Adverse Working Condition" OR "Poor Working Condition" OR "Adverse Work Experiences" OR "Farm*" OR "Agriculture" OR "Fishing" OR "Cheap Labor" OR "Cheap Labour" OR "Occupation" OR "Work" OR "Employ*" OR "Farmers"[Mesh] OR "Mining"[Mesh] OR "Construction Industry"[Mesh] OR "Sex Work"[Mesh] OR "Textile Industry"[Mesh] OR "Plantation" OR "Forestr*" OR "Abuse At Work" OR "Harassment At Work" OR "Work-Related Illness" OR "Informal Labor" OR "Informal Labour" OR "Gig Work" OR "Daily Wage Labor" OR "Daily Wage Labour" OR "Logging Industry" OR "Timber Industry")

#3	Health	("Health"[Mesh] OR "Health Services Accessibility"[Mesh] OR "Access Health" OR "Access To Primary Care"[Mesh] OR "Healthcare Access" OR "Healthcare Visit" OR "Health Facilit*" OR "Health Cent*" OR "Primary Care" OR "Secondary Care" OR "Tertiary Care" OR "Mental Health Servic*" OR "Psychosocial" OR "Psychological Support" OR "Psychosocial Support" OR "Mental Health Support" OR "Psychiatric Care" OR "Social Support" OR "Social Work" OR "Hazard" OR "Injur*" OR "Risk*" OR "Wellbeing" OR "Well-Being" OR "Sick" OR "Ill" OR "Occupational Health")
#4	Countries	(Afghanistan[MeSH Terms] OR Bahrain[MeSH Terms] OR Djibouti[MeSH Terms] OR Egypt[MeSH Terms] OR Iran[MeSH Terms] OR Iraq[MeSH Terms] OR Jordan[MeSH Terms] OR Kuwait[MeSH Terms] OR Lebanon[MeSH Terms] OR Libya[MeSH Terms] OR Morocco[MeSH Terms] OR Oman[MeSH Terms] OR Pakistan[MeSH Terms] OR Qatar[MeSH Terms] OR "Saudi Arabia"[MeSH Terms] OR Somalia[MeSH Terms] OR Sudan[MeSH Terms] OR Syria[MeSH Terms] OR Tunisia[MeSH Terms] OR "United Arab Emirates"[MeSH Terms] OR Yemen[MeSH Terms] OR Türkiye[MeSH Terms] OR Turkey[MeSH Terms] OR "Middle East"[Mesh] OR "Africa, Northern"[Mesh] OR "Arab World"[Mesh] OR "North Africa" OR "Arab Region" OR "Eastern Mediterranean Region" OR "Greater Middle East" OR "Middle East and North Africa" OR "Middle East and Northern Africa" OR "MENA")

String number	Keyword	Syntax (Title/Abstract/Keywords)
#1	migration related euphemisms and proxies	(Migra* OR Immigra* OR Transient OR Migrant OR Refugee OR Emigrant OR Immigrant OR (Undocumented NEXT Immigrant) OR (Undocumented NEXT Migrant) OR (Illegal NEXT Migrant) OR Non-Citizen OR "Non Citizen" OR "Non Native" OR Non-Native OR Foreign OR Resident OR (Asylum NEXT Seek*) OR Asylum OR (Unaccompanied NEXT Minor) OR (Unaccompanied NEXT Migrant) OR Undocumented OR Illegal OR Irregular OR "Third Country Nationals" OR "Unaccompanied Migrant Child" OR (Labor NEXT Migra*) OR (Labour NEXT Migra*) OR (Immigrant NEXT Work*) OR (Economic NEXT Migra*) OR (Economic NEXT Immigra*) OR (Migratory NEXT Status))
#2	Labor exploitation related terms	((Labor NEXT Exploit*) OR (Labour NEXT Exploit*) OR (Exploitative NEXT Practic*) OR Exploitation OR "Exploitative Labor" OR "Exploitative Labour" OR (Human NEXT Traffick*) OR "Trafficking In Human Beings" OR (Sex NEXT Traffick*) OR (Labor NEXT Traffick*) OR (Labour NEXT Traffick*) OR (Child NEXT Traffick*) OR Traffick* OR "Forced Labor" OR "Forced Labour" OR "Coerced Labor" OR "Coerced Labour" OR "Child Labor" OR "Child Labour" OR "Indentured Servitude" OR "Debt Bondage" OR "Domestic Servitude" OR "Domestic Work" OR "Modern Slavery" OR "Manual Low-Skilled Jobs" OR "Low Skilled" OR "Low-Skilled" OR "Workplace Hazard" OR "Hazardous Work" OR Dehumanization OR Coercion OR "Occupational Accident" OR "Working Condition" OR "Occupational Exposure" OR "Workplace Violence" OR "Precarious Employment" OR "Seasonal Worker" OR "Low Wages" OR Underpayment OR Labor OR Labour OR "Adverse Working Condition" OR "Poor Working Condition" OR "Adverse Work Experiences" OR Farm* OR Agricultur* OR Fish* OR "Cheap Labor" OR "Cheap Labour" OR Occupation OR Work OR Employ* OR Mining OR Construction OR "Sex Work" OR Textile OR Plantation OR Forestr* OR "Abuse At Work" OR "Harassment At Work" OR "Work-Related Illness" OR "Informal Labor" OR "Informal Labour" OR "Gig Work" OR "Daily Wage Labor" OR "Daily Wage Labour" OR "Logging Industry" OR "Timber Industry")
#3	Health	(Health OR (Health NEXT Services NEXT Accessibility) OR (Access NEXT Health) OR (Access NEXT To NEXT Primary NEXT Care) OR (Healthcare NEXT Access) OR (Healthcare NEXT Visit) OR (Health NEXT Facilit*) OR (Health NEXT Cent*) OR (Primary NEXT Care) OR (Secondary NEXT Care) OR (Tertiary NEXT Care) OR Psychosocial OR (Psychological NEXT Support) OR (Psychosocial

		NEXT Support) OR (Mental NEXT Health NEXT Support) OR (Mental NEXT Health NEXT Service*) OR (Psychiatric NEXT Care) OR (Social NEXT Support) OR (Social NEXT Work) OR Hazard OR Injur* OR Risk* OR Wellbeing OR (Well NEXT Being) OR Sick OR Ill OR (Occupational NEXT Health))
#4	Countries	Afghanistan OR Bahrain OR Djibouti OR Egypt OR Iran OR Iraq OR Jordan OR Kuwait OR Lebanon OR Libya OR Morocco OR Oman OR Pakistan OR Qatar OR "Saudi Arabia" OR Somalia OR Sudan OR Syria OR Tunisia OR "United Arab Emirates" OR UAE OR Yemen OR Türkiye OR Turkey OR "Eastern Mediterranean region" OR "Middle East" OR "Greater Middle East" OR "Middle East and North Africa" OR "Middle East and Northern Africa" OR MENA OR "Northern Africa" OR "North Africa" OR "Arab world" OR "Arab region"

Scopus

String number	Keyword	Syntax (TITLE-ABS-KEY #1 + #2, TITLE-ABS-KEY-AUTH #3)
#1	Migrant related terms	(Migra* OR Immigra* OR Transient OR Migrant OR Refugee OR Emigrant OR Immigrant OR "Undocumented Immigrant" OR "Undocumented Migrant" OR "Illegal Migrant" OR "Non Citizen" OR "Non-Citizen" OR "Non Native" OR "Non-Native" OR Foreign OR Resident OR "Asylum Seek*" OR Asylum OR "Unaccompanied Minor" OR "Unaccompanied Migrant" OR Undocumented OR Illegal OR Irregular OR "Third Country Nationals" OR "Unaccompanied Migrant Child" OR "Labo?r Migra*" OR "Immigrant Work*" OR "Economic Migra*" OR "Economic Immigra*" OR "Migratory Status")
	Labor exploitation related terms	("Labo?r Exploit*" OR "Exploitative Practic*" OR Exploitation OR "Exploitative Labo?r" OR "Human Traffick*" OR "Trafficking In Human Beings" OR "Sex Traffick*" OR "Labo?r Traffick*" OR "Child Traffick*" OR Traffick* OR "Forced Labo?r" OR "Coerced Labo?r" OR "Child Labo?r" OR "Indentured Servitude" OR "Debt Bondage" OR "Domestic Servitude" OR "Domestic Work" OR "Modern Slavery" OR "Manual Low-Skilled Jobs" OR "Low Skilled" OR "Low-Skilled" OR "Workplace Hazard" OR "Hazardous Work" OR Dehumanization OR Coercion OR "Occupational Accident" OR "Working Condition" OR "Occupational Exposure" OR "Workplace Violence" OR "Precarious Employment" OR "Seasonal Worker" OR "Low Wages" OR Underpayment OR Labo?r OR "Adverse Working Condition" OR "Poor Working Condition" OR "Adverse Work Experiences" OR Agricultur* OR Fish* OR "Cheap Labo?r" OR Occupation OR Work OR Employ* OR Farm* OR Mining OR Construction OR "Sex Work" OR Textile OR Plantation OR Forestr* OR "Abuse At Work" OR "Harassment At Work" OR "Work-Related Illness" OR "Informal Labor" OR "Informal Labour" OR "Gig Work" OR "Daily Wage Labor" OR "Daily Wage Labour" OR "Logging Industry" OR "Timber Industry")
#2	Health related terms	(Health OR "Health Services Accessibility" OR "Access Health" OR "Access To Primary Care" OR "Healthcare Access" OR "Healthcare Visit" OR "Health Facillit*" OR "Health Cent*" OR "Primary Care" OR "Secondary Care" OR "Tertiary Care" OR Psychosocial OR "Psychological Support" OR "Psychosocial Support" OR "Mental Health Support" OR "Mental Health Service*" OR "Psychiatric Care" OR "Social Support" OR "Social Work" OR Hazard OR Injur* OR Risk* OR Wellbeing OR "Well Being" OR Sick OR Ill OR "Occupational Health")

#3	Countries	(Afghanistan OR Bahrain OR Djibouti OR Egypt OR Iran OR Iraq OR Jordan OR Kuwait OR Lebanon OR Libya OR Morocco OR Oman OR Pakistan OR Qatar OR "Saudi Arabia" OR Somalia OR Sudan OR Syria OR Tunisia OR "United Arab Emirates" OR UAE OR Yemen OR Türkiye OR Turkey OR "Eastern Mediterranean region" OR "Middle East" OR "Greater Middle East" OR "Middle East and North Africa" OR "Middle East and Northern Africa" OR MENA OR "Northern Africa" OR "North Africa" OR "Arab World" OR "Arab Region")
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Web of Science

String number	Keyword	Syntax Topic = (Abstract, author, title, keyword)
#1	Migration and related terms	(Migra* OR Immigra* OR Transient OR Migrant OR Refugee OR Emigrant OR Immigrant OR "Undocumented Immigrant" OR "Undocumented Migrant" OR "Illegal Migrant" OR "Non Citizen" OR "Non-Citizen" OR "Non Native" OR "Non-Native" OR Foreign OR Resident OR "Asylum Seeker" OR Asylum OR "Unaccompanied Minor" OR "Unaccompanied Migrant" OR Undocumented OR Illegal OR Irregular OR "Third Country Nationals" OR "Unaccompanied Migrant Child" OR "Labor Migra*" OR "Immigrant Work*" OR "Economic Migra*" OR "Economic Immigra*" OR "Migratory Status")
#2	Labor exploitation related terms	("Labor Exploit*" OR "Labour Exploit*" OR "Exploitative Practic*" OR Exploitation OR "Exploitative Labor" OR "Exploitative Labour" OR "Human Traffick*" OR "Trafficking In Human Beings" OR "Sex Traffick*" OR "Labor Traffick*" OR "Labour Traffick*" OR "Child Traffick*" OR Traffick* OR "Forced Labor" OR "Forced Labour" OR "Coerced Labor" OR "Coerced Labour" OR "Child Labor" OR "Child Labour" OR "Indentured Servitude" OR "Debt Bondage" OR "Domestic Servitude" OR "Domestic Work" OR "Modern Slavery" OR "Manual Low-Skilled Jobs" OR "Low Skilled" OR "Low-Skilled" OR "Workplace Hazard" OR "Hazardous Work" OR Dehumanization OR Coercion OR "Occupational Accident" OR "Working Condition" OR "Occupational Exposure" OR "Workplace Violence" OR "Precarious Employment" OR "Seasonal Worker" OR "Low Wages" OR Underpayment OR Labour OR Labor OR "Adverse Working Condition" OR "Poor Working Condition" OR "Adverse Work Experiences" OR Farm* OR Agricultur* OR Fish* OR "Cheap Labor" OR "Cheap Labour" OR Occupation OR Work OR Employ* OR Mining OR Construction OR "Sex Work" OR Textile OR Plantation OR Forestr* OR "Abuse At Work" OR "Harassment At Work" OR "Work-Related Illness" OR

		"Informal Labor" OR "Informal Labour" OR "Gig Work" OR "Daily Wage Labor" OR "Daily Wage Labour" OR "Logging Industry" OR "Timber Industry")
#3	Health related terms	(Health OR "Health Services Accessibility" OR "Access Health" OR "Access To Primary Care" OR "Healthcare Access" OR "Healthcare Visit" OR "Health Facilit*" OR "Health Cent*" OR "Primary Care" OR "Secondary Care" OR "Tertiary Care" OR "Mental Health Service*" OR Psychosocial OR "Psychological Support" OR "Psychosocial Support" OR "Mental Health Support" OR "Psychiatric Care" OR "Social Support" OR "Social Work" OR Hazard OR Injur* OR Risk* OR Wellbeing OR Well-Being OR Sick OR Ill OR "Occupational Health")
#4	Countries	(Afghanistan OR Bahrain OR Djibouti OR Egypt OR Iran OR Iraq OR Jordan OR Kuwait OR Lebanon OR Libya OR Morocco OR Oman OR Pakistan OR Qatar OR Saudi Arabia OR Somalia OR Sudan OR Syria OR Tunisia OR "United Arab Emirates" OR UAE OR Yemen OR Türkiye OR Turkey OR "Eastern Mediterranean region" OR "Middle East" OR "Greater Middle East" OR "Middle East and North Africa" OR "Middle East and Northern Africa" OR MENA OR "Northern Africa" OR "North Africa" OR "Arab World" OR "Arab Region")

Google Scholar – limited to first 200

("Migrant" OR "Immigrant" OR "Transient" OR "Refugee" OR "Emigrant" OR "Undocumented Immigrant" OR "Undocumented Migrant" OR "Illegal Migrant" OR "Non Citizen" OR "Non-Citizen" OR "Non Native" OR "Non-Native" OR "Foreign" OR "Resident" OR "Asylum Seeker" OR "Asylum" OR "Unaccompanied Minor" OR "Unaccompanied Migrant" OR "Undocumented" OR "Illegal" OR "Irregular" OR "Third Country Nationals" OR "Unaccompanied Migrant Child" OR "Labor Migrant" OR "Labour Migrant" OR "Immigrant Work" OR "Economic Migrant" OR "Economic Immigrant" OR "Migratory Status")

AND

("Labor Exploitation" OR "Labour Exploitation" OR "Exploitative Practice" OR Exploitation OR "Exploitative Labor" OR "Exploitative Labour" OR "Human Trafficking" OR "Trafficking In Human Beings" OR "Sex Trafficking" OR "Labor Trafficking" OR "Labour Trafficking" OR "Child Trafficking" OR "Trafficking" OR "Forced Labor" OR "Forced Labour" OR "Coerced Labor" OR "Coerced Labour" OR "Child Labor" OR "Child Labour" OR "Indentured Servitude" OR "Debt Bondage" OR "Domestic Servitude" OR "Domestic Work" OR "Modern Slavery" OR "Manual Low-Skilled Jobs" OR "Low Skilled" OR "Low-Skilled" OR "Workplace Hazard" OR "Hazardous Work" OR "Dehumanization" OR "Coercion" OR "Occupational Accident" OR "Working Condition" OR "Occupational Exposure" OR "Workplace Violence" OR "Precarious Employment" OR "Seasonal Worker" OR "Low Wages" OR "Underpayment" OR "Labor" OR "Labour" OR "Adverse Working Condition" OR "Poor Working Condition" OR "Adverse Work Experiences" OR Farm* OR "Agriculture" OR "Fishing" OR "Cheap Labor" OR "Cheap Labour" OR "Occupation" OR "Work" OR "Employment" OR "Farmer" OR "Mining" OR "Construction Industry" OR "Sex Work" OR "Textile" OR "Plantation" OR "Forestry" OR "Abuse At Work" OR "Harassment At Work" OR "Work-Related Illness" OR "Informal Labor" OR "Informal Labour" OR "Gig Work" OR "Daily Wage Labor" OR "Daily Wage Labour" OR "Logging Industry" OR "Timber Industry")

AND

("Health" OR "Health Services Accessibility" OR "Access Health" OR "Access To Primary Care" OR "Healthcare Access" OR "Healthcare Visit" OR "Health Facility" OR "Health Cent" OR "Primary Care" OR "Secondary Care" OR "Tertiary Care" OR "Mental Health Service" OR Psychosocial OR "Psychological Support" OR "Psychosocial Support" OR "Mental Health Support" OR "Psychiatric Care" OR "Social Support" OR "Social Work" OR "Hazard" OR "Injur" OR "Risk" OR "Wellbeing" OR "Well-Being" OR "Sick" OR "Ill" OR "Occupational Health")

AND

("Afghanistan" OR "Bahrain" OR "Djibouti" OR "Egypt" OR "Iran" OR "Iraq" OR "Jordan" OR "Kuwait" OR "Lebanon" OR "Libya" OR "Morocco" OR "Oman" OR "Pakistan" OR "Qatar" OR "Saudi Arabia" OR "Somalia" OR "Sudan" OR "Syria" OR "Tunisia" OR "United Arab Emirates" OR "UAE" OR "Yemen" OR "Türkiye" OR "Turkey" OR "Eastern Mediterranean region" OR "Middle East" OR "Greater Middle East" OR "Middle East and North Africa" OR "Middle East and Northern Africa" OR "MENA" OR "Northern Africa" OR "North Africa" OR "Arab World" OR "Arab Region")